

EFFECT OF PROBIOTICS ON PATIENTS WITH INSULIN RESISTANCE

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ABSTRACT

In the last few years, the study of intestinal microflora in patients with prediabetes, obesity and insulin resistance has been of particular importance. Obesity and its associated diseases are still one of the leading causes of disability and death. The human gastrointestinal tract is a complex ecosystem consisting of host cells, intestinal microflora and nutrients. The aim of our study was to study the microbiome of patients with insulin resistance and to observe the change in Homa index based on its correction using probiotics. Based on our research, we can conclude that the long-term inclusion of probiotics in the treatment of patients with insulin resistance for 12 weeks with the following combination: *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*- 1.0×10^9 , *Lactobacillus casei*- 1.0×10^9 , *Lactobacillus acidophilus*- 1.0×10^9 , *Bifidobacterium bifidum*- 1.0×10^9) 6 caps. per day, significantly reduces dyspeptic symptoms, at the expense of loss of appetite and weight loss, reduces body mass index. It also helps to reduce the waist circumference, which can probably be explained by the burning of fat deposits deposited by probiotics. In patients with insulin resistance, taking probiotics for a long time - at least 12 weeks, reduces the degree of insulin resistance and improves the quality of life.

Keywords: Probiotics, gut microbiome, Insulinresistance.

In the last few years, the study of intestinal microflora in patients with prediabetes, obesity and insulin resistance has been of particular importance, since a close correlation between carbohydrate metabolism and the microbiome has been revealed [11] [15]

Obesity and its associated diseases are still one of the leading causes of disability and death, so it is necessary to search for new ways, to study new mechanisms, which may have a transformative effect on the treatment of the above diseases.

The human gastrointestinal tract is a complex ecosystem consisting of host cells, intestinal microflora and nutrients [7]. About 100 trillion bacteria in the intestinal tract make up the intestinal microbiota. Intestinal microbiota consists of many types of bacteria. Gastro-intestinal system is a barrier between potentially toxic substances present in blood vessels [2] Most of the bacteria in the intestine are anaerobic, that's why their number increases with the decrease of oxygen in the water. The distal part of the intestine is the best environment for the growth of bacteria. Food has a great influence on microbes [3] [8]. Intestinal flora is generally stable and has a strong ability to adapt. They have a variety of mechanisms of action in our body, one of the most important of which is to have a positive effect on metabolic processes [12] According to the literature, it is known that certain types of probiotics, specially created strains, have a positive effect on obesity [1][10]

The aim of our study was to study the microbiome of patients with insulin resistance and to observe the change in Homa index based on its correction using probiotics.

At the first stage, we detected gastro-intestinal complaints in patients with insulin resistance, which we did using specially developed questionnaires. The

questionnaire consisted of 10 simple questions, e.g. Do you have diarrhoea, constipation, heart palpitations, feeling like you get bloated easily, etc. We identified patients with 3 or more complaints to form the core group. In order to properly observe changes in insulin resistance, we considered it a necessary condition that the patients included in the study were not treated with specific drugs. In the treatment we included a probiotic with the following content: *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*- 1.0×10^9 , *Lactobacillus casei*- 1.0×10^9 , *Lactobacillus acidophilus*- 1.0×10^9 , *Bifidobacterium bifidum*- 1.0×10^9 in a dosage of 6 capsules. per day - and we observed the change in the Homa index. The main group received the above probiotics for 3 months. We also selected a control group that was not treated with probiotics.

Statistical processing of qualitative and quantitative data was carried out, which allowed us to determine whether there is a reliable connection between the two variables and what effect the mentioned treatment method has on various indicators. The research material was the data obtained in the research group before treatment and as a result of treatment according to the following indicators, complaints: diarrhea, constipation, flatulence, heartburn, feeling of nausea, rapid weight gain; Bacteriological examination of feces: enterococci, typical intestinal bacteria, lactic acid bacteria, bifidum bacteria, laboratory parameters - Homa index, with the first group and its control group - weight and waist circumference. 14 patients with insulin resistance were included in the study. 6 patients in the control group.

As a result of the statistical research, it was obtained: the average index of the home index decreased by 34.42% in the main group, and by 1.32% in the control group.

Table N1

waist circumference changes in the main group before and after treatment;
Change in waist circumference in the control group at 3-month intervals

Characteristics	Min.	Max.	Med.	Standart deviation	Median.
The main group	88	129	104	12,0	101
The main group after 3 months	84	116	100	9,2	98
Control group	98	112	104	5,1	105
Control group – after 3 months	100	111	106	4,6	108

Table N2

Weight change in the main group before and after treatment;
Weight change in the control group at an interval of 3 months

Characteristics	Min.	Max.	Med.	Standart deviation	Median.
The main group	76	121	95,1	12,1	97,5
The main group after 3 months	76	116	93	11,0	94,5
Control group	76	96	85	6,7	86
Control group – after 3 months	79	98	87	6,5	85

We evaluated the change of the Homa index as a marker of insulin resistance before and after treatment with probiotics. According to the literature [14] insulin resistance decreases under the influence of probiotics, which is confirmed by our work. The reduction of the insulin resistance index is also confirmed by comparing the main and control groups, insulin resistance in the control group increased by 1.32%, which is probably related to the fact that we did not use probiotics in the control group.

In our opinion, the reduction of insulin resistance occurred due to the following reasons: probiotics influence appetite and energy consumption, increase the formation of acetate, propionate and butyrate, which are short-chain fatty acids SCFA [5][13] The use of probiotics regulates the intestinal microbiota by increasing the amount of Bifidobacterium and Lactobacillus, which are directly responsible for the production of SCFA[17] It is also believed that some probiotics can inhibit the absorption of fats, increase the amount of fat

excreted in the feces [4]. Therefore, according to the literature, the release of appetite-regulating hormones, probiotics can stimulate appetite-reducing hormones, in particular, glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) and peptide YY (PYY) release [6]. Increased levels of these hormones cause the burning of calories and fat [9]. Probiotics may also increase levels of fat-regulating proteins, which may lead to reduced fat storage[10] [16]

The average weight in the main group decreased by 2.2%, and in its control group - by 1.36%; Waist circumference: decreased by 4.3% in the main group, increased by 1.4% in the control group.

The research material was also the data obtained before treatment and after treatment in the main group according to the following indicators: bifidum bacteria, lactic acid bacteria, enterococci, intestinal sticks (typical). In the main group, the average rate of lactic acid bacteria, bifidum bacteria and enterococci increases, while in its control group it is unchanged.

Based on our research, we can conclude that the long-term inclusion of probiotics in the treatment of patients with insulin resistance for 12 weeks with the following combination: *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*- 1.0×10^9 , *Lactobacillus casei*- 1.0×10^9 , *Lactobacillus acidophilus*- 1.0×10^9 , *Bifidobacterium bifidum*- 1.0×10^9 6 caps. per day, significantly reduces dyspeptic symptoms, at the expense of loss of appetite and weight loss, reduces body mass index. It also helps to reduce the waist circumference, which can probably be explained by the burning of fat deposits deposited by probiotics. In patients with insulin resistance, taking probiotics for a long time - at least 12 weeks, reduces the degree of insulin resistance and improves the quality of life.

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